

Welcome to the Move2THz Newsletter #3!

June 2026

Stay up to date with the recent progress, key milestones, and exciting updates from the Move2THz team.

Photo © Christophe LEPETIT

Main Highlights of the Third Edition

Move2THz External Advisory Board
Strategic Insights

High-profile International
Dissemination Events (across Europe,
Asia, and North America)

Project Research Outputs and Key
Publications

Interview with Pieter Cardinael on
Project Sustainability

Co-funded by
the European Union

Move2THz is supported by the Chips Joint Undertaking and its members, including the top-up funding by National Authorities of France, Switzerland, Germany, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Belgium, under Grant Agreement n° 101139842.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Newsletter #3
June 2026

About

Sustainable INDIUM PHOSPHIDE (InP) platform and ecosystem upscaling, enabling future mass market (sub-)THz applications.

Move2THz – an ambitious project that will address today’s InP shortcomings and build a mature European ecosystem to obtain a commercially and industry-viable platform for use in various mass-market applications utilizing the higher frequency spectrum towards THz and beyond.

Main objectives:

1)

Provide a competitive facility for high-volume InP manufacturing in Europe that is ready to use in the industry.

2)

Foster and leverage the European ecosystem on InP from the material to the application and widen the market adoption.

3)

Demonstrate an overall CO2 footprint reduction all along the product life cycle, from cradle to grave.

Advancing Sustainability through Move2THz Innovation

The Move2THz project directly supports the policy objectives of the **European Green Deal** – the EU’s roadmap to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. In line with this vision, the project promotes sustainable growth and technological sovereignty by advancing resource-efficient innovation in next-generation semiconductor technologies.

By developing a groundbreaking Indium Phosphide-on-Silicon (InPoSi) platform, Move2THz introduces a new era of high-frequency performance that is both **environmentally responsible** and **commercially viable**. The project reduces dependence on scarce materials, lowers the ecological footprint of manufacturing, and strengthens Europe’s circular economy by creating a fully integrated and sustainable value chain.

Reducing CO₂ Footprint Across the Entire Product Life Cycle

Green Innovation – a key objective of the Move2THz project to achieve sustainable carbon efficiency by reducing emissions throughout the entire product life cycle – from raw material sourcing to production, operation, and end-of-life recycling. This “cradle-to-grave” approach ensures that sustainability is embedded in every phase of technology development.

By optimizing the InP-on-Silicon (InPoSi) manufacturing process, Move2THz lowers energy consumption, minimizes the use of rare materials, and promotes resource-efficient wafer production supported by eco-friendly supply chains within Europe. The project also aims to quantify and demonstrate measurable CO₂ reductions using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodologies to evaluate environmental impact at each stage.

These actions form the foundation for all sustainability efforts within Move2THz – ensuring that high technological performance goes hand in hand with measurable climate impact reduction and long-term environmental responsibility.

Smart and Sustainable Use of Resources

In line with these goals, Move2THz is pioneering new ways to drastically reduce the consumption of Indium Phosphide (InP) – one of the rare and resource-intensive materials in semiconductor manufacturing. Using the **Smart Cut process** and its innovative wafer reclaiming capability, the project enables each InP donor wafer to be reused multiple times, achieving more than a **tenfold reduction in raw material usage**.

This breakthrough not only minimizes production waste and environmental impact but also reinforces Europe’s ability to **secure a sustainable and resilient semiconductor supply** for future generations of wireless technologies. Through such **resource-efficient** innovation, Move2THz demonstrates how advanced microelectronics can drive technological progress while respecting environmental limits and contributing to Europe’s path toward **climate neutrality**.

Together, these efforts illustrate how Move2THz turns the principles of the European Green Deal into tangible results – merging innovation, sustainability, and industrial excellence in a single European success story.

Meetings and Move2THz-Organised Events

Move2Thz General Assembly Meeting

15-16 January 2026
Munich, Germany

On 15–16 January, the Move2THz consortium convened in Munich, Germany, for its General Assembly meeting, marking the completion of the project’s mid-term milestone (M18). The consortium would like to sincerely thank Fraunhofer EMFT for hosting the meeting.

The first day of the meeting focused on reviewing the technical progress achieved during the first half of the project. Partners presented updates on key work packages, highlighting major milestones, challenges, and breakthroughs. The consortium also held its **first External Advisory Board (EAB) meeting**, gathering experts from industry and academia to discuss Move2THz use cases and provide strategic feedback. The EAB includes experts in the fields of applications of Move2THz technology who work at leading-edge companies and institutions. The day concluded with a networking activity and a visit to historic sites in Munich.

The second day was dedicated to planning the next phase of the project, including key objectives and milestones for the coming months. **A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) workshop** supported the alignment of Move2THz innovations with European Green Deal goals. The LCA workshop explored key sustainability challenges and opportunities in ICT, including how efficiency improvements can sometimes lead to increased demand and a larger overall environmental footprint. Discussions also covered net-zero strategies for RF power amplifiers, early comparative LCA findings for InPoSi and bulk InP technologies, material considerations related to Indium Phosphide semiconductors, and the project’s broader approach to reducing environmental impact by integrating LCA into future development activities.

Participants also visited Fraunhofer EMFT to learn about ongoing technological developments and industry collaborations.

The meeting provided an important opportunity for technical exchange, strategic planning, and strengthening collaboration among partners. The consortium now looks ahead to its Review Meeting in France this summer, marking the project’s second year.

Dissemination Events

The WiTECH Centre Day

11 November 2025

Gothenburg, Sweden

On November 11, WiTECH – Wireless Infrastructure Technology Centre at Chalmers hosted its second Centre Day. Researchers, PhD students, and partner companies gathered to highlight a year of successful research projects and strengthened collaboration between academia and industry. Move2THz was presented in an oral presentation by project partners Chalmers University of Technology (Chalmers) and Low Noise Factory (LNF).

3-4 December 2025

Malta

EF ECS 2025

Move2THz participated in the EF ECS Exhibition, where the project was showcased through a presentation session and exhibition pitch on December 4. The event provided an excellent opportunity to engage with researchers, industry stakeholders, and technology enthusiasts, highlighting the project's objectives, ongoing work,

and expected impact on future THz technologies. Move2THz also gained visibility during the EF ECS plenary session, where it was referenced in Soitec's presentation on innovative materials as an example of how advanced semiconductor technologies can enable next-generation applications and strengthen Europe's innovation ecosystem. The exhibition fostered valuable discussion on emerging THz technologies and potential collaborations, further increasing awareness of the project and its role in advancing European innovation in high-frequency electronics. We look forward to continuing these conversations and meeting the community again at EF ECS 2026 in Stockholm.

The 2025 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)

6-10 December 2025

San Francisco, California

Move2THz was represented at the 2025 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM 2025), one of the world's leading conferences in semiconductor device technology, held in San Francisco, USA. As part of the technical programme, project partners presented the paper "InP/GaAsSb Double Heterojunction Bipolar Transistors on Silicon Delivering POUT,SAT > 2.2 W/mm and PAE > 38% at 140 GHz". The work, authored by F. Ciabattini, S. Hamzeloui, A. M. Arabhavi, G. Bonomo, M. Ebrahimi, A. Cercaci, O. Ostinelli, and C. R. Bolognesi, showcased advances in high-performance THz electronics and was published in the official IEEE conference proceedings. The presentation highlighted Move2THz's contribution to cutting-edge semiconductor research and reinforced the project's active engagement with the international scientific community.

7-11 March 2026

Los Angeles, California

The OFC Exhibition

Move2THz was represented at OFC 2026 (Optical Fiber Communication Conference and Exhibition) in Los Angeles, USA, through the exhibition booth of project partner ALBIS Optoelectronics. As one of the world's leading events for optical communications and networking technologies, OFC provided an excellent opportunity to showcase innovations relevant to next-generation communication infrastructures. At Booth #1121, ALBIS presented its advanced high-speed photodiode solutions for 400G and beyond optical networks, highlighting technologies that support the growing performance, reliability, and scalability requirements of future communication systems.

18-20 March 2026

Lyon, France

**PEPR Electronics
Scientific Days**

Move2THz was represented at the PEPR Electronics Scientific Days 2026 in Lyon, France, an international event dedicated to advanced electronics, semiconductor technologies, and photonics research. As part of the workshop “Large-Area Semiconductor Materials for Electronics and Photonics,” project partner Kevin Louarn (Almae Technologies) participated in a round table discussion on the key challenges of semiconductor materials research and its complementarity with industrial innovation. The event provided a valuable platform for exchange between academia and industry, highlighting the importance of collaboration in advancing next-generation semiconductor technologies and strengthening the European electronics ecosystem.

**The 2026 IEEE Silicon Photonics
Conference (SiPhotonics)****13–15 April 2026**

Ottawa, Canada

Move2THz was represented at the 2026 IEEE Silicon Photonics Conference (SiPhotonics 2026) in Canada, where researchers from Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) presented the paper “Analysis of InGaAsP Multi-Quantum Wells Directly Grown on InP-on-Si Wafers for Photonic Integration.” Authored by Jhe-An Lin, Akanksha Kapoor, Marcel Verheijen, Victor Dolores Calzadilla, Kevin Williams, and Yuqing Jiao, the work explored advanced photonic integration technologies based on InP-on-Si platforms, contributing to the development of next-generation photonic-electronic systems. The conference provided an excellent opportunity to disseminate Move2THz research results and engage with the international silicon photonics and integrated photonics research community.

**SiPhotonics
2026**13 – 15 April 2026
Ottawa, Canada

The 2026 International VLSI Symposium

13-17 April 2026

Hsinchu, Taiwan

Move2THz was represented at the 2026 VLSI Symposium on Technology, Systems and Applications (VLSI TSA), held in Hsinchu, Taiwan, from April 13–17, 2026. During the event, Arthur Vandrogenbroek presented the poster “A Theoretical and Experimental Assessment of IMD2-H2 Correspondence Under Memory Effects,” authored in collaboration with partners from Universite Catholique de Louvain and Soitec. Organised by the Industrial Technology Research Institute (ITRI) in technical cooperation with IEEE, the symposium brought together leading experts in semiconductor technology and system applications, providing a valuable platform for knowledge exchange, collaboration, and engagement with the international VLSI research community.

IN-MEMORY (LiM) FUNCTIONALITY IN JUNCTIONLESS FEFETS

kar¹, D. Ganesh¹, R.K. Nirala², M. Gupta¹ and A. Kranti²

Campus, Goa, ²Indian Institute of Technology Indore, India

Email: akranti@iiti.ac.in

FEFET and Pulse Scheme

Methodology

- Input A – Polarization of the Fe layer
- Input B – Gate bias (during read)
- $T_{ox} = 10$ nm (HZO), $L_g = 30$ nm, $T_{ch} = 1$ nm (SiO_2), $V_{DD} = 1$ V, $R_{eq} \approx 5$ k Ω
- NOR Design:
 - 5 V (Initialization, Depletes the channel)
 - $V_{in} = 5$ V results in positive polarization in Fe layer, JL FEFET exhibits low threshold (V_{th}) state
 - $V_{in} = 3$ V results in low polarization in Fe layer, JL FEFET exhibits high threshold (V_{th}) state
- NAND Design:
 - +5 V (Initialization, Accumulates the channel)
 - $V_{in} = -5$ V results in high polarization in Fe layer, JL FEFET exhibits low threshold (V_{th}) state
 - $V_{in} = 3$ V results in low polarization in Fe layer, JL FEFET exhibits high threshold (V_{th}) state

NAND Design @ JL FEFET

$N_{ch} = 10^{18} cm^{-3}$
 $\Phi_{ch} = 5.0$ eV

Error in state 1 for input A=0, B=0 (00)
Inability to erase (depletion of electrons)

$N_{ch} = 10^{18} cm^{-3}$
 $\Phi_{ch} = 4.7$ eV

functional achieved for all (00, 01, 10, 11) states

Moderate doping in midgap workfunction

J2-20

VLSI Paper Topic : A Theoretical and Experimental Assessment of IMD2-H2 Correspondence Under Memory-Effects

Co-author(s) : A. Vandrogenbroek¹, M. Rack¹, F. Allibert², J.-P. Raskin¹

Affiliation : UCLouvain¹, Soitec²

Email : arthur.vandrogenbroek@uclouvain.be

CONTEXT

- H_2 is commonly used to characterize substrate **linearity**
- Limitation due to measurements capabilities (**acquisition at $2f_0$**)
- 2-tones measurements provide an alternative by enabling extraction of **2nd order nonlinearities at lower frequency (IMD_2^- at $f_1 - f_0$)**
- Theoretically, a **6 dB** difference is expected both IMD_2 and H_2 ⇒ Objective: Investigate relation between IMD_2 and H_2

THEORY

General

- DUT transfer function: $s_{out} = X(s_{in}) \cdot s_{in}$
- Nonlinear transfer coefficient: $X(s_{in}) \approx a_0 e^{j\phi_0} + a_1 e^{j\phi_1} s_{in} + a_2 e^{j\phi_2} s_{in}^2 + \dots$
- Phase terms account for memory effects:
 - ✓ Finite carrier response time
 - ✓ Capacitive effects ($Y_C = j\omega C = \omega C e^{j\pi/2}$)
- If $s_{in} = A \cdot (\sin(\omega_0 t) + \sin(\omega_1 t))$:
 - ✓ $|H_{2,f_0}| = |H_{2,f_1}| = a_2 A^2 / 2$
 - ✓ $|IMD_2^-| = a_2 A^2 \cos(\phi_1) \leq a_2 A^2 = |IMD_2^+|$

Substrate

- Large signal modulate electron concentration and Si impedance
- Nonlinear equivalent admittance: $Y_{eq}(V) = G_{eq}(V) e^{j\phi_C} + \omega C_{eq}(V) e^{j(\phi_C + \pi/2)}$
- $\cos(\phi_1)$ factor is impacted by:
 - ✓ Ratio between C_{eq} and G_{eq} modulation
 - ✓ ϕ_C and ϕ_G related to carrier response time ⇒ Difficult to ensure $\cos(\phi_1) \approx 1$ making IMD_2^- an unreliable estimator of H_2

Simulation

- TCAD simulations of 5 k $\Omega \cdot cm$ Si with $4 \mu m$ thick oxide and $Q_{ox} = 5 \cdot 10^{19} cm^{-3}$, using $f_0 = 5.2$ and $f_1 = 5.6$ GHz
- DC bias applied from -5 to 5 V
- $IMD_2^+ \sim 6$ dB above both H_2 and same phase
- IMD_2^- amplitude difference not constant with bias

Measurements

Setup to measure all 2nd order nonlinearities under bias with $f_0 = 5.2$ and $f_1 = 5.6$ GHz (phase not measurable)

Measurement of Trap Rich sample

- IMD_2^- lower than in simulation because capacitive effects dominate more in TR than HR Si bulk sample

J2-21

VLSI Multi-head with M I-V Para Sidhant V Vaz

This paper proposes a deep learning friendly Short Channel IGFET Model for MOSFET technologies, using an ultra-cascaded multi-head architecture with diff- and multi-scale loss. It tackles parameter domain consistency and uses six combined Log-MSE, SMAPE, squared exponential local weighting. Trained with 200K Monte Carlo samples, the model achieves very low errors: between 0.3% and 3.95% for I-V, at multiple technology nodes, across various parameter extraction methods.

Cascaded Inverse and Forward ANN

Parameter extraction for 14 nm node. (a) C_{gs} , V_{th} test derivative, (c) C_{gs} , V_{th} second derivative, (d) C_{gs} characteristics.

I-V Extraction Performance

SET Mode	RMS(%)	MIN(%)	MAX(%)
PS-1 14nm	1.54	0.35	2.78
PS-2 14nm	1.75	0.47	4.38
PS-1 7nm	1.75	0.18	2.89
PS-2 7nm	3.55	0.29	6.37
PS-1 3nm	0.98	0.11	1.58
PS-2 3nm	1.90	0.40	2.65

This work presents a multi-head cascaded deep learning architecture for parameter extraction in advanced MOSFETs. Difficult-to-avoid sub-2% errors for critical parameters (CFS, CF, V_{th} , C_{gs}) are achieved across 7, and 14 nm nodes. The floating normalization samples, offering a scalable alternative to exponential fitting.

1. A. Singhal et al., IEEE TED, vol. 71, 2024
2. A. Ashai et al., IEEE TED, vol. 70, 2023

The 24th National Microwave Days Conference (Journées Nationales Microondes – JNM 2026)

19–22 May 2026

Lille, France

Move2THz was represented at the 24th National Microwave Days Conference (JNM 2026). During the conference, Moussa Cissé from the IMS Laboratory presented the paper “Étude et modélisation électromagnétique de structures de calibrage TRL on-wafer jusqu'à 220 GHz en technologie InP”. The work, carried out in collaboration with the III-V Lab partners, contributes to the development of advanced high-frequency measurement and calibration techniques for future THz applications. The event provided an excellent opportunity to disseminate Move2THz research results and engage with the microwave and THz research community.

The 2026 IEEE International Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference (I2MTC)

26-28 May 2026
Nancy, France

Move2THz was represented at the 2026 IEEE International Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference in Nancy, where project partners from IMS Laboratory and III-V Lab presented the paper “Comprehensive On-Wafer Calibration Methodologies for RF Characterization of InP DHBT Technology up to 220 GHz.” Presented by Moussa Cissé and co-authored by M. Cissé, N. Davy, V. Nodjjadjim, B. Ardouin, C. Mismar, M. De Matos, V. Thary, C. Maneux, F. Marc, C. Mukherjee, and M. Deng. The contribution reflects strong collaboration within the Move2THz consortium and supports the development of advanced measurement capabilities for future communication and sensing applications.

Move2THz Community Insights

Interview with Move2THz Partner Pieter Cardinael (Université catholique de Louvain)

This interview features a postdoctoral researcher from UCLouvain's RF-SOI Group, who shares insights into the university's role in the Move2THz project, with a particular focus on sustainability and the environmental impact of emerging InP-based RF technologies across the ICT value chain.

Could you briefly introduce yourself, your academic background, and the university you represent?

P. Cardinael I am a postdoctoral researcher at UCLouvain since 2025, within the "RF-SOI Group" led by Pr. Jean-Pierre Raskin and Pr. Dimitri Lederer. I obtained my PhD in 2024 on the topic of substrate-related parasitic effects in the GaN-on-Si technology for RF applications. I am now working on emerging RF technologies and their environmental impact. UCLouvain is the largest French-speaking university of Belgium and is located in Louvain-la-Neuve, about 30 km south of Brussels. We also host the technological platform WELCOME, an electrical characterization hub with growing expertise in characterization from DC to 325 GHz.

What is your university's role in the Move2THz project?

P. Cardinael Our group's signature has always been the research of a physical understanding of semiconductor material properties, and their impact on active devices and circuits. Originally active in

the SOI world, we are now extending our reach to other technologies such as GaN-on-Si or, through Move2THz, InP/InPOSi. The variety of the tasks we are involved in within Move2THz represents quite well our wide interests. In WP2, UCLouvain together with INCIZE are responsible for the specific characterization of InP and InPOSi substrates fabricated by SOITEC. The goal is to ensure that their RF properties are not negatively impacting overlying circuitry. In WP4, we will assist the effort of characterizing and modelling the new transistors developed by the partners of the project. Finally, we will design a

demonstrator oscillator circuit in WP5 using ETHZ's InP platform.

What does the name Move2THz stand for, and what do you see as the most innovative or distinctive aspects of this project?

P. Cardinael From a scientific point of view, the integration of an InP layer on a Si substrate raises very interesting research questions and forces us to look beyond our "SOI-blinders". The development of a new technology, potentially opening new market opportunities also requires a broader thinking about its impact.

Figure from the Move2THz LCA Workshop Presentation: Life-Cycle Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions from Smartphones. Source: [N. Moreau, T. Pirson, G. Le Brun, T. Delhaye, G. Sandu, A. Paris, D. Bol and J.-P. Raskin, «Could Unsustainable Electronics Support Sustainability?», in MDPI Sustainability, 2021]

Sustainability is a key topic in your university's broader research work. From your perspective, how does the Move2THz project approach sustainability, and how are sustainability considerations reflected in the technologies and processes being developed?

P. Cardinael Indeed, UCLouvain has been questioning the impacts of ICT and exploring alternative electronics through the works of Pr. David Bol and Pr. Jean-Pierre Raskin. Within Move2THz, the sustainability aspect is mostly considered through the usage of the critical material In and the energy efficiency at high frequency enabled by using InP-based electronics. A task dedicated to the life cycle inventory (LCI) of InP and InPOSi is set up to quantify the environmental impacts of the technologies developed in Move2THz. More precisely, the Smart Cut process promises to reuse the donor InP wafer several times by transferring only a very thin InP layer on a less impactful and cheaper Si wafer. The InP content per wafer is thus significantly reduced compared to InP bulk. Furthermore, InP amplifiers realize at sub-THz frequencies. However, it is important to place such efficiency gains in the context of the future deployment of InP (or InPOSi) technologies to assess the overall environmental impact of their development.

Why is it particularly challenging to assess the environmental impact of ICT systems across their entire life cycle?

P. Cardinael The ICT value chain is incredibly complex. For the fabrication of a single chip, several hundreds of process steps are needed, most of which happen inside foundries and involve highly specialized equipment, materials and energy consumption. Combined with the opacity of the manufacturing processes to external players, the task of life cycle assessment (LCA) practitioners is far from straightforward. Recently, the establishment of a fab model by imec or the use of more aggregated data can be highlighted as steps toward a more transparent assessment of the impact of semiconductor manufacturing.

Using digital devices such as smartphones as an example, where do the main environmental hot spots occur, and what role do integrated circuits play in these impacts?

P. Cardinael For user equipment (e.g. smartphones) that have a relatively short use phase (2-3 years), about 70 % of their global warming potential occurs during the manufacturing phase. ICs account for more than a third of this manufacturing impact. Furthermore, it has been estimated that the ICT sector represents ~3-6 % of the greenhouse gases emissions worldwide, which is comparable with the aviation sector. Putting the numbers together, it appears that as institutions active in semiconductor manufacturing, we have a key role to play. Indeed, all economic sectors must decrease their emissions to maintain the planetary systems within a safe operating space.

Efficiency improvements are often seen as a solution, but they can also lead to rebound effects. How can combining efficiency with sufficiency-oriented choices help reduce the overall environmental impact of emerging ICT technologies?

P. Cardinael The rebound effect can be defined as a mechanism through

which an improvement in a technology's efficiency (of resources, of energy, of emissions) does not necessarily lead to an absolute decrease of the consumption or emission of said resource. This happens because the technology becomes more accessible and thus its usage increases. The rebound effect is well documented for the ICT sector, where more functionality "per silicon area" does not bring a decrease in the number of wafers being sold, but rather the opposite, leading to an overall rise in emissions from the sector over time. Countering the rebound effect is difficult and requires to reflect, ahead of the development, about how the technology will be used. The increase in technology usage should stay limited (an approach that could be labelled as sufficiency) in order for the efficiency gains to have net positive impact (defined as an absolute decrease in consumption or emission). As engineers working on emerging technologies, this exercise and resulting appropriate choices are crucial for reducing our footprint.

We sincerely thank our speaker for taking the time to share these insights and perspectives, and we wish them continued success and inspiration in their future research endeavors.

“
Within Move2THz, the sustainability aspect is mostly considered through the usage of the critical material indium (In)

and the energy efficiency at high frequency enabled by using InP-based electronics.

”

External Advisory Board Provides Strategic Guidance for Move2THz

On January 15, 2026, the Move2THz consortium held its first External Advisory Board (EAB) meeting, marking an important milestone in the project's development. While project partners gathered in person at Fraunhofer EMFT in Munich, the board members joined remotely, enabling broad international participation and diverse expert input.

During the meeting, the consortium presented the latest project progress, technical achievements, and research results, which generated significant interest among the participants. The presentations were followed by an open and constructive exchange on market opportunities, exploitation pathways, and the project's long-term impact. The discussions highlighted the important role of independent expert guidance in supporting the project's strategic direction. Drawing on their extensive industry and research experience, the board members provided valuable recommendations to strengthen the exploitation potential of Move2THz results and ensure their relevance to real market needs.

In addition, they offered important perspectives on standardisation-related activities, helping the consortium assess its position within the evolving technology landscape and identify opportunities for future engagement with relevant standards development initiatives. The feedback provided will support the consortium in shaping future exploitation and standardisation activities, helping to translate project results into real-world applications.

The Move2THz partners sincerely thank all Board members for their valuable engagement and guidance and look forward to continued cooperation as the project moves forward.

The Move2THz project benefits from a strong and diverse External Advisory Board, bringing together representatives from leading industrial organisations and renowned universities:

**Pete Zampardi,
IEEE Fellow**

GaAs & Si R&D
Department at Qorvo

Dr Abdul Rahim

Ecosystem Manager,
PhotonDelta

**Mohand
Ahouche**

Senior Strategic
Advisor – Nokia Bell
Labs, France

**Prof. Madhavan
Swaminathan**

Department Head,
Electrical
Engineering, and
Director of the Center
for Heterogeneous
Integration of Micro
Electronic Systems
(CHIMES), Penn State
University, USA

Ranadeep Dutta

Semiconductor
technologist. Principal
engineer at Qualcomm
Technologies

**Professor Aarno
Pärssinen, IEEE Fellow**

Centre for Wireless
Communications (CWC),
University of Oulu,
Finland

Fredrik Tillman, PhD

Senior Research
Manager, Ericsson AB

Professor Peter Asbeck

The University of California, San Diego, Department
of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Examples of Move2THz Research Outputs Through Publications (2025-2026)

All Move2THz publications are available on our website:
<https://www.move2thz.eu/publications>

Publication, Research Article:

“Thermal strain management of III–V heterostructures grown on InP-on-silicon (InPoSi) substrates”

Authors:

C. Besancon, F. Martin, B. Ghyselen, L. Largeau, F. Fournel, L. Sanchez, T. Bria, O. Mourey, C. Navone, J. Decobert

Abstract:

Hetero-integration of InP-based compound semiconductors on CMOS-compatible silicon is desirable for low-cost large-scale applications. Recently, an approach consisting of integrating a thin InP buffer layer onto a silicon (InPoSi) substrate through direct bonding, followed by epitaxial regrowth on the bonded layer has been developed. It allows us to avoid the two major defects origins, antiphase domains and lattice mismatch, of the direct III–V/Si epitaxial approach. The remaining challenge comes from the difference of coefficients of thermal expansion between InP and Si, leading to a compressively strained InP seed layer at growth temperature. The latter was assessed from the curvature signal registered by metrology during etching on the InP layer at typical growth temperature (640 °C) using a PH₃/CBr₄ mixture. The thermal strain effects on different heterostructures grown by MOVPE on InPoSi were studied by microscopy, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), x-ray diffraction (XRD), and photoluminescence measurements. In particular, regularly undulating surface topology was observed by microscopy, which could be associated with a broadening of the XRD peaks for heterostructures thicker than 1.5 μm. Strain-free InP-based structures were grown on InPoSi by adding 1% of Ga to the InP bulk layers to form an In_{0.99}Ga_{0.01}P alloy lattice-matched at growth temperature to the compressively strained InP bonded seed. The undulation for this strain-engineered film was hardly noticeable by AFM and was, therefore, successfully limited.

AFM scans (1 × 1 and 30 × 30 μm²) after CMP polishing of the InPoSi substrates showing RMS values of 0.11 and 0.07 nm, respectively.

Global view of a 100 mm InPoSi substrate obtained after the Smart-Cut process.

Publication, Journal Article:

Authors:

“InP/GaAsSb Double Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor Characterization and Compact Modelling up to 500 GHz”

Marina Deng, Chhandak Mukherjee, Lucas R´eveil, Akshay M. Arabhavi, Sara Hamzeloui, Colombo R. Bolognesi, Magali De Matos, and Cristell Maneux

Abstract:

This paper presents a new methodology to accurately characterize InP bipolar transistors up to 500 GHz. Following design optimization of RF test structures specifically developed for the on-wafer TRL calibration technique, InP/GaAsSb Double Heterojunction Bipolar Transistors have been successfully characterized up to 500 GHz. Moreover, the HICUM compact model was validated against measurements for different operating conditions and various geometries for the first time up to 500 GHz. The physics-based compact model and the associated scalable parameter extraction flow allowed us to demonstrate the scalability of this THz InP DHBT technology, offering possibilities for further design-level explorations. State-of-the-art cut-off frequencies of this THz transistor technology featuring f_{MAX} reaching 1 THz for transistor geometries with 0.15 μm -emitter-widths were experimentally verified and confirmed by the compact model predictions.

Top-view optical image of the THRU standard dedicated to onwafer TRL calibration for (a) G1 and (b) G2.

Cross-sectional electron micrograph of a DHBT with 150 nm emitter mesa width. The base-collector mesa undercut etch was optimized resulting in a base contact width of 50 nm to reduce the extrinsic B-C capacitance.

**Publication,
Conference
proceedings:**

Authors:

“First Demonstration of InP HBTs on InP-on-Si (InPOSi) Substrate: A Cost-Effective and Sustainable III/V-on-Si Technology for Advanced RF Applications”

A. Vais, A. Kumar, S. Yadav, G. Boccardi, Y. Mols, R. Alcotte, B. Vermeersch, U. Peralagu, C. Roda Neve, B. Ghyselen, B. Parvais, B. Kunert, and N. Collaert

Abstract:

In this work, we present the first demonstration of InP HBTs grown and fabricated on an engineered InPOSi substrate. Physical and electrical characterizations were performed to measure its crystal quality and device performance. We show that the performance of devices fabricated on an InPOSi substrate is close to devices fabricated on a native InP substrates making such a technology suitable for advanced RF applications. Fabricated devices show f_t/f_{max} of ~ 140 GHz/70GHz with BV_{ceo}/BV_{cbo} of 3.5 V/5.5 V at an ON current density of $8\text{mA}/\mu\text{m}^2$.

Simplified sketch of the production of InPOSi wafers.

a) A $2 \times 2 \mu\text{m}^2$ AFM scan (and corresponding rms values) of the top device surface on InP and InPOSi substrates, b) A high-angle annular dark-field scanning (HAADF-S) TEM image of InP HBT stack grown on InPOSi with insets representing (top): InP/GaAsSb/InP interface, (bottom): InP/InGaAs/InP interface.

Publication, Conference proceedings:

“High-Efficiency Beyond-110-GHz-Bandwidth 4-Vppd InP-DHBT Linear Modulator Driver for Beyond-200-GBd Optical Transceivers”

Authors:

R. Hersent, F. Blache, F. Jorge, V. Nodjiadjim, N. Davy, C. Mismar, M. Riet, L. Lotti, A. Rylyakov, A. Konczykowska, and B. Arduin

Abstract:

We report on a beyond-110-GHz bandwidth 4-Vppd output swing linear modulator driver, implemented in 0.5- μm indium phosphide (InP) double heterojunction bipolar transistors (DHBT). Using an R-C base ballast in the output stage, the opencollector driver shows reduced (excess) gain peaking, group delay variation and improved stability above 50 GHz. To the authors’ knowledge, this driver achieves the highest reported output stage efficiency FoM of 7.4 GBd and the best complete-IC efficiency FoM (2.3 GBd) and THD (2.8% at 4-Vppd) for beyond-100-GHz bandwidth lumped drivers, without any Digital Signal Processing.

(a)

(b)

InP DHBT linear driver (a) die microphotograph (b) detailed schematic. The output stage uses $2 \times 0.5 \times 7 \mu\text{m}^2$ DHBTs, all others are $0.5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$.

High-symbol-rate linear modulator driver state-of-the-art, [2]–[10]. Results with and without DSP have empty and filled markers, respectively. InP and SiGe implementations are plotted with triangles and squares, respectively.

Publication, Conference Poster:

Authors:

“Benefits of On-wafer Calibration for RF Characterisation of InP DHBT Technology Devices”

Cisse Moussa, Davy Nil, Nodjiadjim Virginie, Ardouin Bertrand, Mismar Colin, Maneux Cristell, Marc François, and Deng Marina

Abstract:

In this study, calibration methods are performed on passive structures up to 110 GHz using off-wafer standards and on-wafer standards. The open and short transistor interconnect measurements are analyzed through a comparison with the electromagnetic (EM) predictive simulation. The results clearly demonstrate the benefits of utilizing on-wafer calibration methods to improve measurement accuracy by significantly reducing the parasitic effects due to the transistor’s interconnects.

Picture of a Pad-Open structure used for on-wafer TRL calibration.

Material stack used for EM simulation of Open and Short structures: a) stack cross section, b) 3D view of the simulated Open structure.

Publication, Conference Proceedings:

Authors:

“InP DHBT AMUX Integrated Circuits for Beyond-200-Gbaud Optical Communications”

Romain Hersent, Qian Hu, Agnieszka Konczykowska, Mohand Achouche, and Bertrand Ardouin

Abstract:

This paper reports on key considerations for analog multiplexers (AMUX) implementation in next generation >200-Gb/s coherent optical TRx. The impact of Nyquist Pulse Shaping and clock jitter on the AMUX SNDR is studied up to 280 Gb/s.

AMUX Selecting Cell Schematic (a) Modified Gilbert Cell. (b) Transimpedance Stage (TIS) Load.

AMUX Selecting Cell simulated (a) normalized differential AC gain (b) PAM-4 SNDR versus symbol-rate at 280 GSa/s with NPS and at 1 sample per symbol (SpS), i.e. without NPS. The SNDR is normalized to its maximum value.

Publication, Conference Proceedings:

Authors:

“Fabrication and development of InP HEMTs on silicon substrate based on a new integration technique”

Francesco Fortunato, Nelson Rebelo, Claire Besançon, Florence Martin, Bruno Ghyselen, Jean Decobert, Johan Bergsten and Helena Rodilla

Abstract:

Current methods for transferring III-V technology onto silicon are based on wafer bonding techniques. Here we explore fabrication applicability of traditional InP-based High Electron Mobility Transistors (InP HEMTs) on InP-on-Si (InPoSi) wafers developed by Smart Cut, a method for transferring InP onto Si that reduces cost and fabrication complexity. We fabricated 100-nm gate length InP HEMTs, including test structures and Hall bars on both InPoSi and InP wafers. Transfer Length Method (TLM) measurements for InPoSi and InP bulk wafers showed comparable contact and sheet resistances. These preliminary results show that InP HEMTs can be fabricated on InPoSi.

Cross-sectional schematic of the HEMT on InPoSi substrate showing the epitaxial structure (not to scale).

Microscope picture of a fabricated 2x20 μm InPoSi HEMT showing the intrinsic two-finger device, together with pads for RF probing.

Publication, Conference Proceedings:

Authors:

“Analysis of InGaAsP Multi-Quantum Wells Directly Grown on InP-on-Si Wafers for Photonic Integration”

Jhe-An Lin, Akanksha Kapoor, Marcel Verheijen, Victor Dolores Calzadilla, Kevin Williams, and Yuqing Jiao

Abstract:

Defect-free InGaAsP multi-quantum wells were epitaxially grown on InP-on-Si wafers with quality comparable to InP wafers. However, the InGaAsP separate confinement heterostructure (SCH) showed 5% less phosphorus to be latticematched with InP; growth-temperature calibration can mitigate these deviations, enabling direct active-passive integration on silicon.

Full active epitaxial layer stack on the InPoSi wafer.

Publication, Research Article:

Authors:

“n+ Doped In_{0.53}Ga_{0.47}As Using Di-Tert-Butylsilane in a Vertical MOVPE Reactor”

Alexander Possberg, Fabian van Essen, Hao Zhang, Jonas Watermann, Jonathan Abts, Jan Ebbert, Konrad Mueller, Patrick Häuser, Lisa Liborius, Nils Weimann

Abstract:

In this work, a systematic study for silicon doping of InGaAs via the metalorganic di-tert-butylsilane (DTBSi) as a non-gaseous alternative to common gaseous precursors in a vertical close-coupled showerhead metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE) reactor is conducted. At a growth-temperature of 620 °C, doping concentrations up to $n = 2.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and electron mobility up to $\mu_n = 1831 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ are achieved. It is found that, in the used reactor geometry, the doping process is mainly limited by the low decomposition of DTBSi, causing low incorporation efficiency compared to disilane. By increasing the reactor pressure from 100 to 200 mbar, it is possible to reduce the growth temperature by 40 K while achieving a doping concentration of $n = 2.8 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ with an electron mobility of $\mu_n = 1631 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$. A similar, although less pronounced effect can be observed when increasing the total carrier-gas flow into the reactor. Increasing growth rate and V/III ratio are also found to enhance the dopant incorporation.

a) Measured (black) and simulated (red) HR-XRD pattern of the (004) reflex of an exemplary sample; b) correlation between extracted InGaAs thickness from HR-XRD measurements and in-situ reflectivity; c) correlation between sheet resistance values determined from TLM and van-der-Pauw measurements.

Move2THz

SUBSTRATES ▶

EPITAXY ▼

DESIGN DEMONSTRATOR

◀ DEVICE

Key Facts

Duration	Start date	Number of partners	Total budget	EU budget contribution
36 months	2024 06 01	27	€ 40,67 M	€ 11,96 M

Discover More Extensive and Up-To-Date Information on Our Website

move2thz.eu

Move2THz is supported by the Chips Joint Undertaking and its members, including the top-up funding by National Authorities of France, Switzerland, Germany, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Belgium, under Grant Agreement n° 101139842.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.